

Munir's Socioecoethical Model (MSEEM) of Human Rights Education (HRE)

Note: This model has received appreciation from The Commonwealth, The Open University, The University of Lagos, Istanbul Zaim University, the British Council, SIMA Academy, and UNESCO. As of May 2023, the momentum of this model has increased significantly in the shape of a free online certificate course. To date, the course has been completed by 1500 teachers and educators from over 75 countries.

Introduction

MSEEM is the culmination of a decade-long effort to document and observe HRE practices in various teaching and learning environments. Using grounded theory, the author gathered HRE perspectives from learners and practitioners in over 47 developing and developed countries via netnography, resulting in the emergence of MSEEM.

MSEEM has taken an integrative, dialectical, and utilitarian approach to introduce HRE to teachers, educators, learners, and anyone, who wishes to disseminate HR values to wider communities through the lens of social consciousness.

MSEEM applies to all levels and types of education, in both developed and developing countries.

While existing human rights education models, theories, and frameworks have been effective in promoting human rights values in some developed countries, they may not always be appropriate for others due to socio-cultural differences. Additionally, not all stakeholders are being adequately involved or included in the process. For instance, the World Program for Human Rights Education has initiated a multi-phase approach. The first phase targeted the primary and secondary school systems, followed by the second phase encompassing higher education, civil servants, law enforcement officials, and the military. The third phase addressed media professionals and journalists, while the fourth phase emphasized youth empowerment. However, there is a pressing need to prioritize sustainability and consistency by ensuring the inclusion of all stakeholders in each phase.

Models based on Western perspectives may lead to cultural sensitivity. It is therefore important to conduct a contextual needs-based assessment to ensure that global models do not overshadow localized knowledge, values, and authentic practices.

Definition of Human Rights Education

According to Munir Moosa Sadruddin, "HRE is a conscious incessant socio-cognitive and eco-ethical learning process that gradually empowers individuals about the rights of self and others. It involves a readiness to make rational and civilized decisions through the conscious filtration of HR ideologies, sociocultural context, and political will. It is a critical component to

achieving sustainable development, maintaining human dignity, and applying social justice. It permeates a sense of openness towards embracing multiculturalism, pluralism, and diversity”.

About the Model

This tripartite model [möbius strip] conjoins social, ecological, and ethrical elements that interact dialectically for building resilience and supporting HRE practices.

Recognizing the importance of sociocultural structures and self-actualization is crucial to embracing and practicing common social rights. Similarly, developing an ecological identity narrative offers insights into personal identity and relationships with social, cultural, political, and economic environments. Ethics, in this context, is an individual pursuit of critical self-discovery. While personal values evolve through experience and exposure, they are often rooted in social and relational identities. It demands individuals take ownership and filter them through the personal and collective lens.

In Sadruddin’s viewpoint, HRE is situated in context. Existing HRE practices must be revamped with an integration of socioecoethical concepts into HRE curricula followed by glocalize knowledge and skills, to develop a deeper understanding of how human rights are interconnected and are essential for creating a just and sustainable world.

As formal and non-formal education opportunities are not universally accessible to all due to escalated educational poverty, the informal method must also be taken on board to infuse human rights values. According to Munir, “We need to dismantle the social construct that regards HRE as an elite subject for the privileged, by blurring the boundaries to its dissemination”.

Many people are aware of the fragility of their rights and are often subject to discrimination, hindering their ability to learn and understand HR practices and take civilized actions. Failing to accommodate human rights education in informal educational settings risks leaving young

minds, adults, individuals belonging to marginalized communities, and elderly people susceptible to violence. Therefore, it is essential to incorporate informal human rights education to promote positive human rights values that are culturally appropriate and inclusive.

Phases

In certain regions, specific factors may discourage policymakers from promoting human rights values. Moreover, many developing and underdeveloped nations oppose Western human rights laws and values, perceiving them as a potential threat to their cultural value systems. Therefore, the journey of HRE should begin with an assessment of the sociocultural context and political will- examining the socio-political and ideological practices of a country, the state of human rights, and cultural perspectives on human rights values.

Next, it is important to assess the dynamism of the ecological environment, including the convergence (social acceptance) and divergence (sensitivities) of human rights, the risks and opportunities of teaching human rights, and the policies and practices related to human rights education at multiple levels. This includes evaluating the state of human rights education (curriculum, courses, units, training module- direct and indirect) and its impact on an individual's well-being, the community, and the policy-making process.

During the ethrical stage, individuals are expected to actively engage in the process of ethical decision-making through the application of critical thinking skills. Ecological identity exploration is crucial to facilitate this process. This involves examining one's relationship with the surroundings and understanding the impact of one's actions on the world around them. By exploring ecological identity, individuals can develop a greater sense of responsibility and accountability for their actions and decisions. This, in turn, helps to promote a more ethical and sustainable approach to decision-making in HRE.

In the fourth phase, a combination of cyber ethnography, netnography, and field study can be employed to assess an individual's general understanding, attitudes, and preferred areas of human rights learning.

Sadrudin argues that human rights educators often extract or adapt the best practices or models of human rights curricula from other countries, which may not adequately address the specific needs of a particular country. This approach can lead to the setting of lofty goals and the creation of momentum within the bureaucracy, which may fail to address context-based issues.

After initial filtration, decisions about the content of HRE should be made with consideration of the local context. The course should begin by discussing fundamental concepts, such as basic rights, human rights values, and movements, particularly in the local context. When discussing HR laws and policies, HRE movements, and their existing state, local complexities, and opportunities should be considered. The course must then include filtered global human rights values to help learners recognize the interconnectedness of human rights issues around the world and appreciate the diversity of cultures and experiences. This approach will provide learners with contextual understanding and relevance, increasing their likelihood of actively engaging in informed and constructive actions that can bring about positive change.

To ensure a comprehensive and culturally relevant approach to HRE, it is crucial to gather and filter pertinent resources (both formal and informal). A recommended approach is to prioritize the collection of local knowledge and then filter and supplement it with suitable global human

rights content that aligns with the sociocultural context of the country. While the adaptation of resources may be necessary, they must remain socio-culturally appropriate. To this end, the development of localized open educational resources is necessary to promote sustainable open educational practices in HRE.

Essential competencies and skills empowerment such as critical thinking, decision-making, situation analysis, social and voluntary skills, digital literacy, counseling skills, mental health well-being, peacebuilding, and negotiation, green education, peace leadership, and environmental literacy must be negotiated within and beyond the cultural context. Heutagogy, peeragogy, and case-study-based approaches are three potential teaching strategies that can be effective in various contexts.

Finally, teaching HRE alone does not ensure peace and unity in the world. The actual litmus test is reflected through attitudes and actions in a sustainable way, and that is challenging to evaluate.

Munir asserts that the absence of familial or social identity can exacerbate grievances, which may further escalate when individuals lack the skills to manage internal conflicts. In such cases, it is vital to build resilience.

Munir's socioethical model of human rights education focuses on empowering individuals about human rights rationally and contextually. By adopting this model, there is a potential to foster a more inclusive society.

Dr. Munir pioneered 'loglocal' approach to teaching HRE. This approach aims to promote a deeper understanding and appreciation of HRE by first building on learners' existing knowledge and experiences of their local cultures, societies, policies, and practices. This is done to ensure that the content being taught is relevant and meaningful. Once learners develop a strong understanding of HR in local context, the loglocal approach then introduces them to global knowledge and perspectives on HR. This helps to broaden their perspectives of HRE through the lens of multicultural and social contexts. The loglocal approach also emphasizes the importance of adapting global content to local contexts.

This is done by encouraging learners to critically examine global perspectives and to identify ways in which they can be applied to their communities. This ensures that the content being taught is not only relevant but also culturally sensitive and respectful.

<https://sites.google.com/view/munir-moosa-sadruddin>

